

Welcome to Our First Cybersphere Insights edition!

We are thrilled to share the latest milestones from COcyber, a project funded under the EU's Digital Europe Programme, committed to strengthening collaboration between civilian and defence cybersecurity sectors. As we move forward, we aim to foster a resilient cybersecurity ecosystem that addresses Europe's critical digital challenges.

COcyber Highlights

Since day one, we have been fully committed to making an impact. Our team met in person for the first physical **General Assembly** in Brussels this October, where we reviewed early achievements, celebrated our first milestones and looked ahead to what's next!

We've launched the 👉 [COcyber website](#), with a first phase offering essential information about our project goals, activities, and updates. In the future, phase two will transform the platform into a one-stop shop for **European cybersecurity**, featuring detailed resources on key actors, funding opportunities, and governance initiatives.

[Discover the goals and vision driving the Cocyber platform!](#)

To strengthen collaboration, an initial [needs assessment](#) is underway to gather insights from key stakeholders. Led by Solvay Business School, the consultations include focus groups with defense representatives, SMEs, regulators, and industry experts. These sessions will **identify gaps and opportunities for improved cooperation between sectors**, ensuring that COcyber initiatives are aligned with Europe’s evolving cybersecurity needs.

Additionally, we’ve launched the [COcyber Ambassador Programme](#), which aims to **bring together top professionals in the cybersecurity sector to promote collaboration and awareness**. From next January onwards, a pool of selected ambassadors play a crucial role in amplifying our mission, sharing updates, and fostering connections across Europe.

Event Participation – Widening Reach

COcyber has been actively engaging with the cybersecurity community. Highlights include participation in the [ENISA Cybersecurity Awareness Raising Conference](#), the [EIT Digital Deep-Techers](#), the [CSDP Annual Training and Education Conference](#), [Navigating Cyber Storms: Civilian and Defence Synergy in a Digitalised World](#) and the [Cybersecurity@CEPS SUMMIT 2024](#).

These events provided valuable opportunities to meet professionals, for dialogue and knowledge-sharing to advance our objectives while bringing a contribution to building a more secure digital Europe.

Cyber News Digest

ENISA Biennial Report [The State of Cybersecurity in the Union](#) provides a comprehensive overview of cybersecurity maturity and recommendations to address critical gaps in policy implementation, skills, and supply chain security.

Cybersecurity professionals: new opportunity to strengthen cybersecurity skills in the EU. The European Commission launched a call for expression of interest to join the new [Industry-Academia Network](#) under the Cyber Skills Academy. This initiative is designed to bridge the cybersecurity skills gap in the EU by boosting collaboration between academia and industry

Opportunities from our network

We shine a spotlight on our sister project, [ECYBRIDGE](#), which shares the same commitment as COcyber to advance the EU's goals of a secure and resilient digital future. By uniting cybersecurity efforts across civilian and defence sectors, ECYBRIDGE fosters collaboration, knowledge-sharing, and innovation to tackle shared threats through a cohesive approach..Don't miss out - follow their journey [here!](#)

What's next

Looking ahead, we're eager to continue building momentum with your support. Stay connected for more updates, and join us to contribute your expertise in driving innovation and collaboration to enhance Europe's cybersecurity resilience!

⚡ Don't miss any opportunities, and register now at <https://cocyber.eu/user/register> !

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